

EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS OF DAMAGE IN FABRIC-REINFORCED COMPOSITES SUBJECTED TO LOW-VELOCITY IMPACTS

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1 Introduction

Fabric-reinforced composites (FRCs) have become one of the most important structural materials in various industries due to a unique combination of properties such as excellent stiffness, high strength-to-weight ratio and impact strength, good resistance to fracture and ease to manufacture shapes tailored for specific applications. Hence, they are now broadly used in aerospace and naval structures as well as in automotive, construction and energy industry; there is an increasing use of them in sports products. In service, components and structures, containing composites, can be exposed to different loading conditions including dynamic events, e.g. impacts. Such loading can cause deterioration of structural integrity and load-bearing capacity due to induced damage. Because of their heterogeneity and microstructure, composite laminates usually demonstrate multiple modes of damage and fracture when compared with more traditional, macroscopically homogeneous, structural materials such as metals and alloys. Among damage and fracture modes are fibre breaking, transverse matrix cracking, debonding between fibres and matrix and inter-ply and intra-ply delamination.

2 Experimental Methods and Results

This study deals with analysis of damage in two types of laminates – carbon fabric-reinforced polymers (CFRP) and glass fabric-reinforced polymers (GFRP) – under impact bending [1, 2]. The materials studied were laminates with twill 2/2 woven balanced and symmetric fabrics made either of carbon or glass fibres reinforcing thermo-plastic polyurethane (TPU) polymer matrix. The material was manufactured from 0°/90° prepreps in the form of four plies designated as [0°/90°]_{2s}, where 0° and

90° represent yarns in the warp and weft directions, respectively.

Dynamic bending tests in a low-velocity range from 1.5 m/s to 2 m/s as experienced by the sports products were carried out according to the ASTM D 4812 standard using an instrumented pendulum type CEAST Resil impactor. Un-notched rectangular specimens of 40 mm length, 25 mm width and 1.0 mm thickness were prepared from CFRP and GFRP laminates. In the dynamic tests, the bottom of the specimen was fixed firmly in a machine vice as a cantilever beam; whereas the upper 30 mm of the specimen was hit with the striker of the pendulum hammer with a controlled level of initial energy, resulting in large-deflection bending of the specimen. The distance between the fixed support and the line of contact of the hammer's striking nose was kept at 22 mm according to the standard. A calibrated impact hammer with a mass of 0.6746 kg and a length of 0.3268 m was used in this work. Impact tests were performed on CFRP and GFRP specimens at energy levels of 0.1 J - 0.6 J and 0.1 J – 1.1 J, respectively, to determine the energy inducing ultimate fracture of the specimens. A piezoelectric force transducer was fixed rigidly to the hammer's striking nose to capture the impact-force signal. The signal was registered with a pre-defined sampling frequency of 227 kHz, with up to 5000 data points recorded per impact test by the data acquisition system DAS 8000 connected to the Resil impactor.

The impact force-time response of CFRP specimens tested at six different energy levels is presented in Fig. 1. From these plots, it is clear that the slope and the peak load of the force-time curve increased with increase in impact energy. At low energy levels, there is a linear increase of force with the time at the start of loading, representing a purely elastic undamaged response of the specimen. The loading and unloading portions of the curves had a nearly

symmetric parabolic shape up to 0.4 J, indicating that very little damage occurred.

As the impact energy was increased to 0.5 J, fluctuations in the force-time history could be observed before the peak load was reached. These fluctuations associated with load drops represent the internal damage initiation such as delamination at low incident energy with an associated loss in the laminate stiffness [3]. As the load continued increasing, the damage grew and multiple delaminations at different ply interfaces could occur. The curve became unsymmetrical at 0.5 J with regard to their peaks as can be seen in Fig. 1. The force-time curve showed more oscillations due to significant damage before the fabric fracture occurred at 0.6 J impact energy. The fabric rupture was represented by a sudden drop in contact force implying a momentary loss of contact between the impactor and specimen due to tensile fracture of fibres at the front face (impacted tension side) of the specimen. The dynamic response of GFRP specimens tested at energy levels 0.1 J – 1.1 J is shown in Fig. 2. The material shows no significant damage till 0.4 J. As the impact energy is increased, a Hertzian failure can be observed at the start of the impact events after 0.8 J. The specimens tested at 0.8 J – 1.1 J energies also exhibited a permanent deflection after testing, which may be due to the visco-elasto-plastic nature of the glass fibres apart from the TPU matrix.

In dynamic tests of CFRP specimens, the contact durations remained almost the same with increase in the impact velocity. Such a response indicates that the material's behaviour is strain rate-independent under dynamic loading in fibre-dominated modes as was also observed in [4]. However, the on-axis GFRP specimens exhibited a rate dependent behaviour as the contact duration increased with the impact energy (see Fig. 2). The peak loads for CFRP specimens were higher than that of GFRP at the corresponding energy levels due to the material's stiffness. The higher stiffness also resulted in lower contact durations for CFRP specimens than those for GFRP at the respective impact energy levels. Further, GFRP composites did not exhibit a catastrophic fracture like CFRP composites but rather deformed permanently at higher impact energies. This means that although GFRP composites are less strong but they sustain a wide range of impact energy before being seriously

collapsed. These results suggest that in dynamic tests, a given peak impact force can be obtained by varying impact velocity for a constant hammer mass, while a required contact duration can be obtained by choosing the appropriate material's stiffness. In the next sections, the damage behaviour of only CFRP laminates is studied with micro-CT and FE simulations.

3 Micro Computed Tomography for Damage Characterization

In this study, X-ray micro-CT measurements of tested CFRP specimens were performed using an XT H 225 X-ray scanner. The system consists of an X-ray detector and an electronic X-ray source, creating 2D cross-sections of the object. The source is a sealed X-ray tube operating at 25–225 kV with a 3 μ m spot size. Following acquisition of tomographic data of the sample, a software program built a precise 3D map from 2D radiograph images by 'stacking' the individual slices one on top of the other; this process is known as reconstruction. As denser materials absorb more X-rays than voids and air, this attenuation contrast allows detection and characterization of cracks and flaws in tomographic images. A small sample with dimensions of 8.5 x 6.0 x 1.0 mm (W x H x T) was prepared from the impacted region of the CFRP specimen tested at 0.5 J. Additionally, two small samples, one of size 7.90 x 6.10 x 1.0 mm from the fractured region and second of size 8.31 x 6.50 x 1.0 mm from the impact region of the CFRP laminate tested at 0.6 J were prepared.

Data for the samples was collected at 80 kV and 85 μ A. Transmission X-ray images were acquired from 3600 rotation views over 360° of rotation (rotation step of 0.1°) for 3D reconstruction. The data was reconstructed using CT-Pro software, and the resulting 3D volumes were analyzed using the commercial software VG Studio Max 2.2 to segment and highlight regions of interest.

The reconstructed 3D images of the impacted CFRP specimen at the bending (fractured) location under 0.6 J impact energy are shown in Fig. 3. Realization of inter-ply and intra-ply damage mechanisms at outer edge, 25%, 50%, and 75% of the sample's width is shown in Figs. 3a, b, c, and d, respectively. Dark grey regions in images represent cracks and

damage whereas light grey areas represent higher density material i.e. carbon-fiber tows.

It was shown that before ultimate fracture, the laminate exhibited matrix cracking and then delaminations and tow debonding. Matrix cracks developed in the weak resin-rich pockets around the tows. Inter-ply delamination and intra-ply delamination such as tow debonding can also be observed. These delaminations normally appeared near the matrix cracks area, which suggested that the formation of cracks initiated delamination. In the fiber-rich regions, damage was apparently linked to debonding at the fiber/matrix interface. The analysis of internal structure showed that at the time of fabric fracture which was triggered by tensile fiber failure, almost every ply was delaminated.

This delamination is more pronounced in Figs. 3a and c than in 3b and d. The reason is that warp tows, which are aligned along the beam axis, bear a higher load than transverse weft tows in bending of the specimen under impact. Similarly, tomographs presented in Fig. 4 show matrix cracking, delamination and tow debonding at the hammer's impact location along the specimen height. At the impact location (Fig.4c), the interface on the impact side (specimen's front side) is more damaged, which is different to the conical form of damage from bottom to top in drop-weight impact tests studied in [3, 5]. Dents in the tows below the striker are also visible. All the tomographs showed that matrix cracking, delamination and tow debonding were the prominent damage modes at the specimen's impact location, whereas at the bending location, these modes were coupled with fabric fracture.

4 Numerical Simulations

The complex weaving architecture as well as multiple modes of damage at various length scales in woven composites makes the micro-mechanics-based constituent-level modeling more computationally expensive for a real-size problem. Thus, a meso-level modeling approach dealing with homogeneous orthotropic plies and a cohesive interface connecting two adjacent plies was adopted to investigate the macro-level response of specimens with dimensions used in tests. Such a meso-level approach coupled with CDM was used in [6-8] to characterize the damage behavior of fabric-reinforced composite structures. Here, a discrete

modeling approach based on the CZM rather than CDM is employed to realize the out-of-plane fabric fracture apart from the interface delamination and their interaction, without any compromise on the global behavior of the structure.

In this study, two 3D FE models – Models A and B as shown in Fig. 5 – were developed to simulate a dynamic behavior of damaged and fractured CFRP specimens at impacts with energy levels 0.5 J and 0.6 J, respectively. In Model A of the damaged specimen at 0.5 J impact energy, cohesive-zone elements were introduced at the resin-rich interfaces between the laminate's plies. Hence, Model A contained three longitudinal cohesive layers - one in front of the beam's neutral plane (NP), the second coinciding with it, and the third to the back of the NP to simulate multiple delamination scenarios. Model B (fractured specimen at 0.6 J) had, in addition to same three interface layers, one more through-thickness transverse cohesive layer placed at the specimen fracture location, to model both the inter-ply delamination and intra-ply fabric fracture and their interaction. The following notation is used for cohesive layers in Models A and B: FCL - in front of the NP (towards impact face), MCL - the cohesive layer coinciding with the NP, and BCL - the one to the back of the NP; the through-thickness transverse layer is denoted as CCL. These cohesive layers were included in the model since the location of damage initiation is a priori known from the micro-CT analysis. Since CFRP composites are essentially strain rate-independent in fiber-dominated modes such as on-axis $[0^\circ, 90^\circ]_{2s}$ laminates subjected to in-plane tension and compression in the low-velocity (low strain-rate) regimes, the material constants obtained from the quasi-static tests (Table 1) were used in the FE models. Similarly, the cohesive law was assumed to be strain-rate insensitive, and thus static fracture-toughness values were assumed for a dynamic crack growth; this was proven to be sufficient in previous dynamic fracture studies [9].

The modeled test set-up, geometry, mesh and boundary conditions of FE models are shown in Fig. 6. A reference point at the pivot of the hammer along the axis of rotation was created and then tied with the hammer's cylindrical surface through kinematic constraints. All translations and rotations of the pivot node were constrained except rotation about z-axis to simulate the hammer's center of

rotation as shown in Fig. 6(b). The initial angular velocities of 5.33 rad/s and 5.81 rad/s were applied to the whole hammer, corresponding to the impact energies of 0.5 J and 0.6 J in Models A and B, respectively. The degrees of freedom of the specimen's bottom were constrained in such a way that the supports allow shrinkage due to the Poisson's effect and replicate its boundary conditions in the vice (Fig. 6b). The hammer was discretized with 4-noded linear tetrahedron C3D4 elements, whereas the specimen was meshed with 8-noded linear brick C3D8R elements using a structured meshing technique. Inter-ply and intra-ply cohesive layers were meshed with 8-noded bilinear COH3D8 elements. A structured converged mesh of 0.2 mm x 0.2 mm was defined in the plane of the specimen at the impact and fracture locations, while a biased mesh was at other regions. The specimen as well as the hammer was considered as deformable bodies. The impactor's striking surface and the specimen's surface referred as S1 and S2 in Figs. 6c and 6d, respectively, were defined as master and slave surfaces, respectively, in defining contacts in all FE models. The FE meshes of Models A and B contained a total of 187,634 and 268,365 elements, which took 22 and 30 hours, respectively, to run simulations on the HPC cluster of 36 CPUs. A separate numerical analysis on Model A was performed to investigate the effect of boundary conditions on the dynamic response of laminates. Here, the top edge of the specimen was fully constrained to create the conditions of fixed-fixed beam under dynamic bending. Further details of the FE modeling can be seen elsewhere [10].

Cohesive-zone elements (CZEs) were used to model both the inter-ply and intra-ply damage modes and their interaction in CFRP laminates. The nominal quadratic stress criterion was used for damage initiation. Damage propagation was based on the Benzeggagh and Kenane criterion [11]. Parameters of the cohesive zone elements presented in Table 2 were taken from the authors' previous work [1]. Apart from inter-ply damage modeling, CZEs have also been used to model intra-ply damage mechanisms such as splitting and ply fracture in composite laminates [12]. Here, the initiation of intra-ply fabric damage was linked to average ultimate flexural strength of 720 MPa in both warp and weft directions as observed in bending tests. Intra-ply fracture evolution was based on fabric

fracture energy of 40 kJ/m² in both warp and weft directions as reported in [7] for a similar carbon fabric. The stiffness of finite-thickness cohesive elements was calibrated according to , proposed by Daudeville *et al.* [13], where (8 GPa) is the material's through-thickness stiffness and which is 16 μm (taken from [10]) is the thickness of resin-rich interface between plies; resulting in interface stiffness of 5 x 10¹⁴ N/m³ for inter-ply damage. However, stiffness of the interface elements defined for intra-ply fracture was based on the longitudinal elastic stiffness E11 of the ply instead of E33 in the above relation resulting in a higher value of 1x10¹⁵ N/m³.

A comparison between the experimental and numerical force-time responses of the damaged CFRP specimen at impact energy of 0.5 J is shown in Fig. 7. Fluctuations in the experimental force-time history designated as Fd-Exp representing the internal damage initiation (load drops in Fig. 7) can be observed before the peak load is reached. It can be observed that the global response and the contact times are reasonably well predicted for the damaged specimen. However, the numerical damage threshold Fd-FE, at which a significant change in the laminate stiffness is detected, is under-predicted in the FE model. This discrepancy may be due to the meso-level consideration of the plies in FE formulations. Apparently, in experiments, the woven laminates absorbed more energy due to the resin-rich pockets and the interlacing of fibers in two mutually perpendicular directions, and, thus, offered more resistance to damage initiation, which were not taken into account in the FE model.

Figure 8 shows the predicted delamination area at three interfaces – FCL, MCL and BCL – in simulation with Model A at two different time intervals: at 1 ms (just at Fd-FE; Fig. 8a) and at 6 ms (near peak load; Fig. 8b). Similarly, the evolution of damage area at the impact location calculated from Model A is plotted in Fig. 9. Here, delamination initiated first at the point of hammer impact and then at the bending location of the cantilevered CFRP specimen. Due to sharp corners of the hammer striker, the ends of the trace were damaged more. A large and quick increase in the delamination area was observed simultaneously in all the layers beyond the time corresponding to Fd-FE. It can be seen from both Figs. 8 and 9 that the largest area of delamination occurred at the mid-plane interface

layer MCL due to the high level of through-thickness shear stress. Thus, a Mode-II type delamination initiated in the specimen's mid-region, where shear stress reached the interface shear strength, and grew more in MCL than FCL and BCL at the impact location. Similarly, the maximum bending stresses at the upper (front) and lower (back) plies were foremost responsible for damage formation at FCL and BCL of the specimen, especially at the bending location (Fig. 8). After the load peak is reached at 6.2 ms, the damage growth is stopped in the unloading region of the load-time response (Fig. 9). The size and shape of the individual delaminations could not be compared to their experimental counterparts as such experimental results were not provided by the micro-CT for full-scale specimen due to the requirement of field of view of the system. Also due to the weaving architecture of the laminate, the spread of the damage is not in a 2D plane. Thus, the measurements of delamination crack lengths at the impact location of the specimen tested at impact energy of 0.5 J are compared with the numerical prediction in Fig. 10. The arrows in both images show the position of the impactor. As the width of micro-CT sample was 6 mm, thus, a comparable region of the impact location from Model A is presented here. Although there is a variation in the lengths of the delamination cracks, still, the mid interface layers are more damaged in both the scan and simulations; demonstrating the front-to-back formation of delamination cracks. This also corroborates that the maximum transverse shear stresses at the mid-plane, were largely responsible for the larger amount of delamination inside the specimen.

5 Conclusions

The dynamic behaviour of woven CFRP and GFRP laminates under low-velocity impacts was studied using experimental tests and Micro CT scanning. Experimental results highlighted the energy absorbing capabilities of the composites reinforced with woven fabrics. The micro-structural analysis was performed to observe different damage modes in the impacted specimens using Micro CT, providing a detailed picture of the damage modes and interaction among different failure mechanisms at various locations.

The obtained results show that fracture in CFRP laminates is linked to that of brittle carbon fibres. Though GFRP samples demonstrated damage and nonlinearity at lower impact-energy levels than CFRP, they absorbed more energy without fracture by manifesting permanent deformation even in the on-axis laminates. Further, the contact duration for GFRP specimens was more than that of CFRP due to their low stiffness.

Finite-element simulations allowed a deeper insight in spatio-temporal evolution of damage in fabric-reinforced composites, exposed to dynamic bending loading.

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Table 1. Material properties of twill 2/2 woven CFRP

	E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	E_{33} (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	$G_{13}=G_{23}$ (GPa)	ν_{12}
CFRP	55.0	52.0	8.0	3.8	3.7	0.05
GFRP	21.5	21.0	8.5	3.1	4.1	0.11

Table 3. Material parameters of inter-ply cohesive elements

	Mode I	Mode II
Normalised elastic modulus (N/m ³)	5×10^{14}	5×10^{14}
Inter-ply strength (MPa)	12	26
Inter-ply fracture toughness (kJ/m ²)	0.8	1.75

Fig. 1. Force-time response of twill 2/2 woven CFRP laminate in impact tests

Fig. 2. Force-time response of twill 2/2 woven GFRP laminate in impact tests

Fig. 3. Reconstructed 3D tomographs of twill 2/2 CFRP specimen at bending (fracture) location across width of sample (resolution 6.1 μm): (a) edge; (b) 25%; (c) 50%; (d) 75% of width

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Fig. 4. Reconstructed 3D tomographs of twill 2/2 CFRP specimen at impact location across height of sample (resolution 6.7 μm): (a) edge; (b) 25% (1 mm above impact center line) (c) 50% (at impact center); (d) 75% (below impact center line) of height

Fig. 5. Schematics of FE models for damaged (Model A) (a) and fractured (Model B) (b) behaviors of CFRP specimens tested at 0.5 J and 0.6 J impact energy, respectively

Fig. 6. (a) Test set-up of dynamic bending. Dynamics FE model: (b) 3D geometry with boundary conditions; (c) mesh of hammer; (d) mesh of specimen (specimen is shown larger)

Fig. 7. Comparison of experimental and numerical (Model A) force-time response for CFRP laminates at impact energy of 0.5 J

Fig. 8. Delamination evolution in FE Model A at impact energy of 0.5 J at 1 ms (a) and 6 ms (b)

Fig. 10. Comparison of experimental (micro-CT) (a) and simulated (b) delamination lengths in FE Model A at impact energy of 0.5 J

Fig. 9. Evolution of inter-ply delamination area at the impact location of laminate in FE Model A at impact energy of 0.5 J